

JURIDICAL SCIENCES

MARRIAGE CONTRACT AND ITS SIGNIFICANCE IN THE FAMILY LEGISLATION OF THE REPUBLIC OF AZERBAIJAN

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ABSTRACT

A marriage contract is a contract in which married or newly married couples regulate how their property will be shared during the marriage phase and in the event of their marriage ending in the future. Essentially, it is based on the couple reaching an agreement on the distribution of their property. The marriage contract is considered as a property regime contract in Azerbaijan Civil Law. This contract helps to solve common and future property sharing problems.

Keywords: marriage, family law, contract, property code, human, Republic of Azerbaijan, husband and wife.

A marriage contract is a contract based on the will of the spouses, which determines the activities of the family, the position of the spouses towards each other, the division of property, income and expenses. The real importance of prenuptial agreements is that they determine how property is to be divided upon divorce. A marriage contract is not an obligation on the behavior of the spouses towards each other, but only a contract that regulates their property. The legal equivalent of a prenuptial agreement is a property contract regime, and since the term prenuptial agreement is more commonly used in the community, we have included the term prenuptial agreement.

In the legal literature, different legal scholars have different opinions about the nature of the marriage contract as a legal institution. One of these concepts is the concept of a contract based on the rules and conditions of concluding a legal marriage and the possibility of obtaining compensation as a result of the breach of marriage. This concept is more focused on the use of the contractual regime of the property of the spouses. According to A. I. Zagarovski, one of the legal scholars, both the content of the marriage and its dissolution do not depend on the will of the spouses. According to legal scholar M. Demirchiyeva, it would be more accurate to refer the institution of marriage to a special category of institutions rather than to refer it to the field of contract law. G. F. Shershenevich clearly separates the formation of marriage based on a contract from the marriage-legal relationship [2]. Therefore, both marriage and the creation of civil obligations are based on the contract. As a result, like most legal scholars, both A.I. Zagarovski and G.F. Shershenevich accepted family law as a branch of civil law and marriage as a special type of civil law institution.

As we know, family law rightfully became an independent field of law from the last century. Although family law is closely related to civil law, it is an independent area of law. As an independent field of law, family law regulates a certain type of social relations - family relations, that is, the relations that arise from the fact of marriage and belong to the family. Another concept includes the expression of will aimed at obtaining legal and non-legal consequences of married persons as

a whole. This is primarily based on the social and legal status of legal spouses [3].

By entering into marriage, husband and wife agree in advance to enter into relations, which are mostly determined by law. As a result, the legal nature of marriage allows marriage to be characterized as a contract. It is necessary to distinguish between marriage and legal consequences based on marriage. There is also a concept that has become widespread in recent years. The essence of this concept allows marriage cooperation (partnership). Most authors associate the emergence of this idea with the development movement for women's legal equality, their independent status and, of course, the equality of husband and wife in marriage. Thanks to the mentioned concept, husband and wife in marriage become collaborators (partners).

Family law distinguishes four types of property regimes;

1. Legal regime of acquired property: It is the legal regime of property adopted in Azerbaijan. In other words, if the spouses do not determine the contractual regime between them by concluding a marriage contract, the existence of a legal regime in the acquired property between them is accepted by law. In the acquired property, the property acquired by the spouses during the marriage in the legal regime is considered joint property of the spouses, regardless of who owns it.

2. Division of the contractual regime: During the division of the contractual regime, the parties retain the right to manage, benefit from and dispose of their property within the framework of the law. In other words, whoever owns the property continues to own it after the divorce.

3. Joint property division regime: Joint property division is a special type of property division in which spouses continue to own their property even after divorce. However, unlike other contract regimes, there is a partial cancellation process. In other words, in this type of regime, one of the couples buys back the property held by the other. When the mode of division of shared property is completed, the husband who proves that he has a superior interest may, among other measures, demand the transfer of the jointly owned

property to his wife by paying an amount equal to his share on the due date.

4. Generality of the contract regime: The generality of the contract regime covers the common property of the spouses and the personal property of the spouses. In this type of regime, spouses share all property, whether it is common property or personal property.

Marriage contract is a bilateral legal agreement in formal form that brings the rules regarding the contractual regime of marital property to the extent permitted by law. As a rule, the contractual regime of the property must be officially closed. Marriage contract is popularly known as property contract regime. In other words; This is known as an agreement in which the parties agree on the consequences of divorce before entering into the marriage union. According to Article 39.3 of the Family Code, the marriage contract is concluded in writing and notarized. A marriage contract can be concluded at any time before the state registration of the marriage, as well as during the marriage.

(Article 39.1 of the Family Code) In accordance with this, the time of entry into force of the contract is determined. The entry into force of the marriage contract should be understood as the creation of the property rights and obligations of the spouses stipulated by the contract. According to Article 39.2 of the Family Code, the marriage contract concluded before the state registration of the marriage enters into force from the day of the state registration of the marriage [2]. This means that the parties do not have any rights and obligations based on the marriage contract until the marriage is registered in the Registry Office. If the parties refuse to enter into marriage, the marriage contract concluded before the marriage is annulled.

Thus, a marriage contract concluded before the state registration of the marriage can be considered a contract concluded with the condition of postponing the entry into force of the contract. A marriage contract is a contract that regulates how the property of married or newly married couples will be divided during the marriage phase and in the future in the event of the termination of their marriage. Basically, this is based on the couple agreeing on the division of their assets. The marriage contract is considered as a property contract regime in the Family Legislation of the Republic of Azerbaijan. This agreement helps to solve common and future property exchange problems. Unfortunately, marriages in today's society cannot last for long. For this reason, divorce, which has become an important sociological event in our country, has caused some disputes in the legal process [5].

After divorce, in addition to problems such as material and moral compensation, alimony, guardianship, how to divide the property acquired during marriage, more precisely, cancellation of the contract regime has become one of the important issues of legal acts. The set of rules that regulate the rights and obligations of the spouses over the property they own before the marriage or during the marriage and their disposal of this property when the marriage ends is called the contract regime. However, the contractual regime of property (nuptial agreement) is defined as legal transactions

aimed at choosing or changing the property regime to be applied.

However, the point to be noted here is that marriage contracts are not binding on the behavior of spouses towards each other, but only a contract regulating property rights. In other words, a marriage contract is an agreement concluded between married persons, which defines the property rights and obligations of the spouses during the marriage and (or) when the marriage is broken. With this agreement, the spouses can change the legal regime of joint ownership and apply a joint, shared or separate ownership regime to the common property, its separate types or to the property of each of the spouses. In reality, however, this agreement is rarely made, resulting in numerous problems during the dissolution of the marriage, with loving couples later venting their anger and hatred on each other in courtrooms.

In other words, there are deep social reasons for not concluding a marriage contract, as well as psychological reasons. It seems that the conclusion of the marriage contract is considered as a hint of the future dissolution of the marriage, and therefore the conclusion of this contract is avoided at all costs. However, the existence of a marriage contract could play a role in preventing the parties from breaking the marriage in a number of cases. That is, the marriage contract could become one of the reasons for the decrease in divorces.

According to the family law, the marriage contract can be concluded on the existing and future property of the spouses. The marriage contract is concluded in written form and notarized.

This may be changed or revoked at any time. To change or break the contract, it depends on the mutual consent of the spouses. Upon such agreement, the contract may be modified or terminated at any time. If there is no agreement, the marriage contract can be changed or broken by the decision of the court based on the claim of one of the parties. The marriage contract can be disputed by the husband (wife) if the terms of the contract put him in a very unfavorable situation. With the exception of the duties stipulated in the marriage contract for the period after the dissolution of the marriage, the marriage contract is also terminated from the moment of the termination of the marriage. The marriage contract cannot limit the rights and activities of the parties, their right to appeal to the court [4].

After the marriage contract is concluded, neither party can refuse its execution. However, the marriage contract can be changed or canceled at any time with the consent of the parties, and this consent must be in writing. If the marriage contract is terminated, the couple's rights and responsibilities are terminated in the contract. The rights and responsibilities provided for in the marriage contract may be limited to certain periods, and various conditions may be created. The marriage contract regulates the rights and capacity of the spouses, the right to apply to the court for the protection of their rights, the rights and duties in relation to children, as well as personal non-property relations between the spouses, for the maintenance of the husband (wife) who is in need and unable to work. Provisions that limit the right to receive funds, put one of the

spouses in a very disadvantageous situation and contradict the principles of family law cannot be provided.

Terms of the marriage contract that violate these requirements are irrelevant and are considered invalid from the moment the contract is concluded. A marriage contract can be concluded at any time before the state registration of the marriage, as well as during the marriage. The marriage contract concluded before the state registration of the marriage enters into force from the day of the state registration of the marriage. The marriage contract is concluded in written form and notarized. The marriage contract can be changed or terminated at any time in written form and notarized with the consent of the spouses. It is not allowed to unilaterally refuse the execution of the marriage contract. According to the husband's (wife's) request, the marriage contract can be changed or broken by the court's resolution on the grounds and in the manner provided for the change and violation of contracts by the Civil Code of the Republic of Azerbaijan.

With the exception of the duties stipulated in the marriage contract for the period after the dissolution of the marriage, the marriage contract is also terminated from the moment of the termination of the marriage. A marriage contract can be considered completely or partially invalid by the court on the grounds provided for invalidating contracts by the Civil Code of the Republic of Azerbaijan. If the terms of the contract put the husband (wife) in a very unfavorable situation, the marriage contract can be disputed by him. The provisions of the property contract regime begin after the marriage; As a rule, the contract concluded between the parties continues until the termination of the marriage. However, if the existing property contract regime becomes an emergency property regime (separation of property - by law or by a judge's decision at the request of one of the spouses), or if the spouses choose another property regime by contract, or if there are good reasons, one of the spouses it is available when it is requested from the court [7].

Because the provisions governing the emergency property regime are mandatory, contracts concluded with a prior waiver of the emergency property regime requirement are void. Spouses are responsible for the damage caused by their minor children in the manner determined by civil legislation. The husband (wife) must inform his creditor (creditors) about the conclusion, change and violation of the marriage contract. If the husband (wife) does not fulfill this duty, he is responsible for his obligations regardless of the content of the marriage contract. According to the Civil Code of the Republic of Azerbaijan, the creditor(s) have the right to demand the change of the terms of the marriage contract or its violation.

The Family Code of the Republic of Azerbaijan (Article 38.6) contains a list of conditions prohibited from entering into a marriage contract. According to this norm, the following conditions cannot be included in the marriage contract: a) limiting the rights and activity capacity of the spouses; b) limiting the right of the spouses to apply to the court for the protection of their rights; c) regulating rights and duties in relation to

children, as well as personal non-property relations between spouses; d) limiting the right to receive funds for the maintenance of a husband (wife) who is in need and unable to work; e) puts one of the spouses in a very disadvantageous situation and contradicts the principles of family law [1];

A marriage contract can be concluded on the existing and future property of the spouses. As mentioned, the marriage contract can be concluded before or after the marriage. Although the contract was concluded before the marriage, it takes effect from the day of registration of this marriage. A marriage contract refers to a legal contract that can be entered into personally. That is, the marriage contract cannot be concluded with a power of attorney like certain civil legal contracts. Even in foreign countries, according to the procedure for concluding a marriage contract, this contract must be concluded in writing and the parties must personally sign the contract. In addition, the marriage contract cannot be concluded in favor of third parties, even minors. Because a child has special rights and freedoms as an individual [8].

Along with the national legislation, this situation is also established in international acts. For example, the Convention on the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms includes the right to liberty, the right to justice, the right to equality and the prohibition of all forms of discrimination. It should be noted that according to the law, unless otherwise stipulated in the marriage contract, the property acquired by the spouses during the marriage is their joint property. But different issues can be determined in advance in the marriage contract [6].

The conclusion of a marriage contract in Azerbaijan is not mandatory and is recommended in the legislation. In many cases, couples who want to start a family are almost completely unaware of the benefits of a prenuptial agreement. Newly married couples do not mentally accept the prenuptial agreement and are skeptical that the marriage will be permanent.

Even if one party is willing to do so, he is reluctant to tell the other party that he is considered an unreliable person because of the consequences of a possible divorce in the future. However, the conclusion of the marriage contract insures the parties against disputes that will occur in the future and sometimes last for years in courts, and acts as a guarantor of the future social security of the parties. At the same time, the existence of a marriage contract can play an important role in reducing divorces.

In addition, some experts propose to amend the legislation regarding the mandatory conclusion of the marriage contract. In our opinion, forcing the contract is contrary to the principle of freedom of contract. In this sense, the contract should be concluded with the consent of the parties, without coercion, without the parties being under any influence.

Humans are the only beings that can form social relationships thanks to their ability to use their emotions and reason. As a requirement of social life, people should engage in activities such as working, producing, consuming, buying and selling, and marrying. During these activities, he must interact with his peers.

When people are engaged in such activities, they can naturally have many problems with their fellows. Although people often prefer to solve the problems they face in life with religious and moral values, they are not always successful in this. Law is the only institution that provides a final solution to the problems of individuals with each other and ensures that the owner of the right gets his rights. The following scientific conclusions have been reached as a result of the conducted research:

- The existence of the marriage contract institution in the family legislation of the Republic of Azerbaijan is considered a progressive phenomenon.

- Compared to the practice of foreign countries, it is not in accordance with the family legislation of our Republic that any other family relations can act as the subject of a marriage contract, except the property relations existing between spouses.

- Enforcing the marriage contract is not appropriate as it does not correspond to the principle of freedom of association and the reality of Azerbaijan.

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